

Organizational Conflict Management: Success Strategies and SWOT Analysis

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Abstract

Organizational conflicts present significant challenges, impacting both employee satisfaction and organizational success. Effective resolution strategies are necessary for maintaining a balanced work environment amidst diverse perspectives and potential sources of conflict. This paper aims to explore internal conflicts among employees within organizations, focusing on resolution strategies, their impact on job satisfaction, primary causes, and frequency. Utilizing a quantitative approach, the study involved 238 participants selected through a snowball sampling technique. Data collection relied on close-ended questionnaires, with responses analyzed using chi-square tests. Additionally, the paper examines strategic planning and management techniques to mitigate internal conflicts, employing SWOT analyses to identify associated strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. By providing evidence-based insights and recommendations, this study contributes to the field of organizational conflict management, offering strategies to foster workplace harmony and enhance productivity.

Enter keywords: Organizational Conflict, Conflict Management, Strategic Planning, Conflict Types, Conflict Role, SWOT Analysis

1 Introduction

Organizations may face management challenges and conflicts among staff, partners, and other involved parties while striving to achieve their goals. Conflicts are inevitable due to differing perspectives, beliefs, and backgrounds of individuals involved. Proactively addressing conflicts can promote collaboration and productivity within organizations (Ongori, 2009; Hyatt et al.,

2023). Organizational conflicts frequently stem from historical issues, cultural disparities, diverse work environments, and a range of factors including autonomy, management strategies, and employee remuneration. Dealing with workplace disputes is widespread (Valdes, 2023).

Recognizing conflict types fosters organizational creativity. By prompting policy review and minimizing discord, conflict can drive positive change. Effective management alters conflict situations or individual responses. (Adomi et al., 2005). (Overton & Lowry, 2013) notes that while conflicts can enhance performance and drive essential changes, mismanagement can harm an organization's reputation, induce stress, and reduce productivity. Building on the Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument (Thomas & Kilmann, 1974) which outlines five conflict management styles (avoidance, accommodation, competition, compromise, and collaboration), effective strategies can offer avenues for resolution in knowledge-based organizations. By adjusting conditions and expectations, these approaches can foster positive outcomes even when faced with differing goals and ideologies (Kiitam et al., 2016). Research by Overton et al. (2013) identifies communication breakdowns, personality clashes, workload disparities, and leadership styles as common conflict triggers in such environments. Fortunately, various resolution strategies exist to address these issues, including direct communication, mediation, and conflict management training for both employees and project managers (Maiti & Choi, 2018). By implementing these strategies, organizations can restore harmony and maintain productivity.

This study delves into employee conflict resolution strategies, their impact on job satisfaction, primary causes, and frequency within organizations. With a quantitative approach, participants were surveyed using close-ended questionnaires and analyzed through chi-square tests. Additionally, strategic planning and management techniques were explored, employing SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) analyses to identify associated strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. By offering data-supported insights and recommendations, this study contributes to the field of organizational conflict management, aiming to foster workplace harmony and enhance productivity.

2 The Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is to investigate internal conflicts among employees within organizations, focusing on understanding conflict resolution strategies, analyzing their impact on job satisfaction and productivity, identifying primary causes of conflicts, and examining the influence of gender, age, and the area of employees on conflict dynamics. By offering data-supported insights, the study aims to offer recommendations for effective conflict management strategies, ultimately fostering workplace harmony and enhancing organizational productivity.

3 Methodology

This research used a mixed-methods approach (surveys and SWOT analysis) to explore conflict resolution in organizations. A survey (238 participants) measured employee demographics, conflict resolution strategies, job satisfaction, and perceived productivity. Chi-square tests examined relationships between these variables. SWOT analysis provided insights into organizational strengths and weaknesses regarding conflict management. This combined approach offers a comprehensive understanding of conflict resolution.

4 Discussion

Conflicts within organizations arise from diverse perspectives and competing interests, impacting individuals and organizational dynamics. Conflict stems from differing interests or irritation, rooted in conflicting needs. These needs range from superficial desires to fundamental human necessities. Severe conflicts often trace back to basic human needs like identity and control. However, all conflicts share a common element: power dynamics. Whether challenging, resisting, or cooperating, conflicts are fundamentally about establishing or altering power balances in relationships (Deutsch et al., 2006). Effective top management teams require strong communication and problem-solving skills to navigate conflicts constructively, fostering high-quality decision-making and positive team dynamics. By promoting both cognitive and affective conflict resolution, such teams ensure long-term success and overall team contentment (Amason, 1996). Task and relationship conflicts, if unresolved, can impede teamwork and diminish team performance (De Dreu & Weingart, 2003). Ethical decision-making in organizations involves managing conflicts between stakeholder interests, corporate values, and personal morals during periods of change. Building a culture of ethical decision-making through training, open communication, and conflict management is crucial for fostering a healthy work environment (Hyatt et al., 2023).

Organizational conflict as a dynamic process, where a moderate level can stimulate effectiveness. While fear, force, fairness, and financial concerns can trigger conflict, effective managerial conflict resolution fosters a positive and productive work environment (FAO & India Institute of Management, 1997), undergoes phases from initiation to resolution with various impacts (Rahim, 2001). Conflicts can arise between staff, departments, or other organizational components due to diverse reasons. Categorically, conflicts encompass task, relational, and procedural types (S. O'Connell et al., 2009). Task conflicts arise from disagreements over tasks, goals, or structures, potentially impacting productivity, and satisfaction (Patil, 2013). Relationship conflicts stem from interpersonal clashes, hindering team productivity (Roark, 1978). Procedural conflicts emerge from disagreements over project execution, often affecting morale and team performance (Patil, 2013). Conflict resolution, even for substantive and

procedural issues, can boost group productivity by fostering innovation, better procedures, and stronger bonds(Fujishin, 2007).

4.1 Conflict Types and Their Role

There are two types of conflict within organizations: functional conflict and dysfunctional conflict. While functional conflict can be constructive and enhance hierarchical development, dysfunctional conflict hinders organizational development.

4.1.1 Constructive Conflict

Conflicts are integral to decision-making processes and can yield positive outcomes when managed effectively (Gaba & Joseph, 2023). Productive conflict, characterized by open discussions and diverse perspectives, enhances productivity, and fosters innovation within teams (Haeruddin et al., 2023). Contrary to common perception, conflict can serve as a catalyst for positive change if approached constructively (FAO & India Institute of Management, 1997). How conflicts are handled by management significantly influences organizational performance, as conflicts stimulate idea-sharing and problem-solving, leading to improved decision quality and group cohesion (Robbins et al., 2013). Recognizing conflict as an opportunity for growth can enhance organizational effectiveness and performance.

Table 1: The Effectiveness of Constructive Conflict

Flexibility	Open and true	Communication of feelings
Cooperation	Non-judgmental actions	Less stress
Improved team performance.	Commitment to Conflict	Proceeding from natural or Professional knowledge
Active or important resolution of conflict	The needs of both parties are being met	Motivation of a search for new effective resolutions
Supportiveness	Win-and-win resolutions	Respect for others
Focus on matters	Managementimproved	Improved org performance

Source: (FAO & India Institute of Management, 1997; Rahim, 2001; Robbins et al., 2013).

4.1.2 Destructive Conflict

Conflict among team members, irrespective of their organizational hierarchy, detrimentally impacts productivity, leading to negative outcomes. Destructive conflict behaviors, as highlighted by Ayoko et al. (2014), can severely affect both organizations and individual team members. Misalignment of staff responsibilities with organizational goals, as well as discrepancies in values and working environments, can fuel destructive conflicts. When conflicts are mishandled by organizations, adverse effects such as damaged relationships and diminished enthusiasm ensue (Riaz & Junaid, 2011). These behaviors result in unproductive and detrimental outcomes.

Table 2: Behaviors Arising from Harmful Conflict

Judgmental actions	Insults	Anger and frustration
Personal attacks	Incomplete tasks	Diminishing and reducing output
Organizational reputation may damage	Reduced team performance	Weaknesses to smooth working condition
Annoying situations for both	Hindering decision-making processes.	Race and competition among staff members
Attacks may occur in extreme cases	A strike may happen in extreme cases	Temporarily or long-term Shut channels of communication.
Reduced self-confidence.	Inflexibility	

Source: (FAO & India Institute of Management, 1997; Rahim, 2001; Black et al., 2019))

The literature emphasizes the multifaceted nature of organizational conflicts and the need for proactive management strategies to address them effectively. Understanding conflict dynamics and implementing suitable resolution approaches can foster a culture of collaboration, trust, and resilience for long-term success.

5 Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research methodology to investigate internal conflicts within organizations, focusing on frequency, causes, impact, and resolution methods (Musheke & Phiri, 2021; Persefoni & Konstantinos, 2019). A structured questionnaire was distributed among 250 employees in diverse sectors in Rawalpindi, Pakistan, with 238 valid responses analyzed. Sampling utilized snowball sampling, a non-probability technique, due to the difficulty in reaching the target population (Cohen & Arieli, 2011). Statistical analysis explored conflict frequency, severity, and causes (e.g., communication breakdowns, leadership conflicts). The analysis also assessed the impact of conflict on employee satisfaction, productivity, and overall

organizational performance, considering internal conflict resolution strategies (Rahim, 2002). Participants from various organizational levels were included to ensure diversity (Penn State's Department of Statistics, 2024).

The collected respondent data underwent rigorous statistical analysis using techniques such as frequency distributions, descriptive statistics, and chi-square tests. This analysis aimed to uncover underlying relationships and patterns within the dataset, ultimately leading to a deeper understanding of the research topic (Kotronoulas et al., 2023).

5.1.1 Demographic information of Surveyed Variables, Category, Frequency, and Percentage

The table presents demographic characteristics and responses to workplace conflict questions among surveyed employees. Most respondents were aged 31-40 (49.6%), male (68.5%), and from urban areas (66.4%). In terms of workplace conflict experiences, the majority reported conflicts occurring monthly (21.4%) or rarely (31.5%). Communication issues (49.6%) and leadership styles (20.2%) were cited as primary conflict causes, with 49.2% indicating a strongly negative impact on job satisfaction and productivity. Descriptive statistics reveal a relatively narrow age distribution (mean = 2.38, SD = 0.881) and slight skewness towards male respondents and those from urban areas. Additionally, the table includes information on the frequency distribution, descriptive statistics, and chi-square statistics of the internal organizational conflict of employees.

Table 3: Employee Conflict Analysis Summary

Variable	Responders Number	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Sum
Employees Age	238	2.38	2.00	0.881	566
Gender of Respondents	238	1.28	1.00	0.449	304
Area of Employees	238	1.34	1.00	0.473	318
How often do you experience conflicts in your workplace?	238	3.13	3.00	1.341	744
What are the primary causes of conflicts in your workplace?	238	2.05	2.00	1.204	488
How do conflicts impact your job satisfaction and productivity?	238	1.76	2.00	0.911	420
How do you typically resolve conflicts with coworkers or supervisors?	238	1.86	1.00	1.076	443

In terms of conflict resolution strategies, the most reported approach was direct communication, preferred by 52.5% of respondents. Overall, the table provides valuable insights into the demographic composition of the surveyed population and their experiences with workplace conflicts, highlighting the need for effective communication strategies and conflict resolution mechanisms in organizational settings.

Below the table of frequency of Employees Age who replied to the survey questionnaires, it can be observed that the majority of respondents fell within the age range of 21-30, accounting for 38.7% of the total sample. This was followed by the age range of 31-40, comprising 34.5% of respondents. Those aged 10-20 constituted 16.8% of the sample, while respondents aged 41 and above made up 10.1%. This distribution provides insights into the demographic composition of the respondents and allows for a better understanding of the perspectives represented in the study.

Table 4: Age Distribution of Employees

Employees period	Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
10-20		40	16.8	16.8	16.8
21-30		92	38.7	38.7	55.5
31-40		82	34.5	34.5	89.9
41+		24	10.1	10.1	100.0
Total		238	100.0	100.0	

The below table presents the distribution of survey respondents based on their gender. Out of a total of 238 respondents, 172 identified as male, representing 72.3% of the sample, while 66 identified as female, representing 27.7% of the sample. This distribution provides insight into the gender composition of the surveyed population, which is essential for understanding the perspectives and experiences captured in the research data.

Table 5: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender of Respondents	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	172	72.3	72.3	72.3
Female	66	27.7	27.7	100.0
Total	238	100.0	100.0	100.0

The below table illustrates the distribution of survey respondents based on their location of employment. Out of the total 238 respondents, 158 reported working in urban areas, constituting 66.4% of the sample. Conversely, 80 respondents reported working in rural areas, comprising 33.6% of the sample. This breakdown offers valuable insight into the geographic distribution of the surveyed population, providing context for analyzing differences in perspectives and experiences between urban and rural employees.

Table 6: Employee Distribution by Urban and Rural Areas

Area of Employees				
Area of Employees	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Urban	158	66.4	66.4	66.4
Rural	80	33.6	33.6	100.0
Total	238	100.0	100.0	100.0

The frequency table presents insights into workplace conflicts, including occurrence, causes, impact on job satisfaction/productivity, and resolution methods. Notably, a significant proportion report daily/weekly conflicts, primarily due to communication issues, followed by personality clashes and workload/resource allocation. Despite negative impacts, direct communication is the most used resolution method, underscoring the need for effective conflict management.

Table 7: Employee Responses to Conflict Situations

Survey Question	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
How often do you experience conflicts?	Daily	44	18.5	18.5	18.5
	Weekly	31	13.0	13.0	31.5
	Monthly	51	21.4	21.4	52.9
	Rarely	75	31.5	31.5	84.5
	Never	37	15.5	15.5	100.0
What are the primary causes of conflicts?	Communication issues	118	49.6	49.6	49.6
	Personality clashes	38	16.0	16.0	65.5
	Workload and resource allocation	34	14.3	14.3	79.8

	Leadership and management styles	48	20.2	20.2	100.0
How do conflicts impact your job satisfaction and productivity?	Strongly Negative Impact	117	49.2	49.2	49.2
	Negative Impact	76	31.9	31.9	81.1
	Positive Impact	29	12.2	12.2	93.3
	Neutral	16	6.7	6.7	100.0
How do you typically resolve conflicts with coworkers or supervisors?	Direct communication	125	52.5	52.5	52.5
	Mediation	45	18.9	18.9	71.4
	Escalation to management	51	21.4	21.4	92.9
	Avoidance	10	4.2	4.2	97.1
	Others	7	2.9	2.9	100.0

6 Results

The table presents the frequency distribution, descriptive statistics, and inferential statistics (chi-square test) related to organizational internal conflicts among employees, focusing on issues such as insufficient organizational communication, leadership challenges, workload, their impacts, and resolution strategies. A total of 250 employees were initially considered for inclusion in the study, out of which 238 responders were selected for analysis.

6.1.1 Gender of Respondents

The analysis of workplace conflict perception and navigation by different genders revealed disparities in conflict resolution strategies, impacts on job satisfaction and productivity, primary causes of conflicts, and frequency of conflict experiences. Male respondents leaned towards direct communication for resolution while female respondents preferred mediation. Additionally, male respondents reported slightly higher daily or weekly rates of experiencing conflicts compared to their female counterparts.

Table 8: Gender-Based Responses to Conflict Resolution Strategies, Job Satisfaction Impact, Primary Conflict Causes, and Conflict Frequency

Survey Question and Response	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender of Respondents * How do you typically resolve conflicts with coworkers or supervisors?			
Direct communication	125	52.5	52.5
Mediation	45	18.9	71.4
Escalation to management	51	21.4	92.9
Avoidance	10	4.2	97.1
Others	7	2.9	100.0
Gender of Respondents * How do conflicts impact your job satisfaction and productivity?			
Strongly Negative Impact	117	49.2	49.2
Negative Impact	76	31.9	81.1
Positive Impact	29	12.2	93.3
Neutral	16	6.7	100.0
Gender of Respondents * What are the primary causes of conflicts in your workplace?			
Communication issues	118	49.6	49.6
Personality clashes	38	16.0	65.6
Workload and resource allocation	34	14.3	79.9
Leadership and management styles	48	20.2	100.0
Gender of Respondents * How often do you experience conflicts in your workplace?			
Daily	44	18.5	18.5
Weekly	31	13.0	31.5
Monthly	51	21.4	52.9
Rarely	75	31.5	84.4
Never	37	15.5	100.0

These findings suggest that gender may influence not only the approaches taken to resolve conflicts but also the frequency and perception of conflict experiences in the workplace. Understanding these gender-specific dynamics is crucial for developing tailored interventions and strategies aimed at promoting effective conflict management and fostering a harmonious work environment for all employees.

Table 9: Statistical Analysis of Conflict Factors: Chi-Square Test Results for Conflict Resolution Strategies, Impact on Job Satisfaction, Primary Causes of Conflict, and Frequency of Conflict

Factor	Chi-Square	df	p-value	Notes
Conflict Resolution Strategies	10.241	4	0.037	Statistically significant association
Impact on Job Satisfaction	9.23	3	0.026	Statistically significant association
Primary Causes of Conflict	9.533	3	0.023	Statistically significant association
Frequency of Conflict	13.211	4	0.01	Statistically significant association

The analysis of the Gender of Respondents variable provided significant insights into workplace conflict dynamics, revealing statistically significant associations ($\chi^2 = 10.241$, $\chi^2 = 9.23$, $\chi^2 = 9.533$, $\chi^2 = 13.211$) with p-values of 0.037, 0.026, 0.023, and 0.01 respectively. These associations were observed in conflict resolution strategies, impact on job satisfaction, primary causes of conflict, and frequency of conflict experiences. Gender plays a pivotal role in determining preferred resolution methods, perceptions of conflict effects, sources of conflicts, and their frequency, highlighting the nuanced influence of gender in shaping workplace conflict dynamics.

Fig. 1 Bar Charts Showing Gender-wise Distribution of Conflict Resolution Strategies, Impact on Job Satisfaction, Primary Causes of Conflicts, and Frequency of Conflicts

In summary, the results underscore the importance of considering gender dynamics in understanding and addressing workplace conflicts. Recognizing these gender-specific patterns can inform targeted interventions and strategies aimed at promoting effective conflict management and fostering a positive work environment for all employees.

6.1.2 Employees Age

The analysis of employees' age reveals significant trends in conflict dynamics. Younger employees, aged 10-20, show a greater inclination towards mediation while those aged 31-40 tend to escalate conflicts to management more often. Job satisfaction is notably affected across

different age groups and communication remains the key conflict trigger. Conflict frequency varies with daily conflicts being most frequent among employees aged 31-40 and the highest monthly incidence reported by those aged 10-20.

Table 10: Employee Distribution by Age Groups and Conflict Factors

Employees Age	Conflict Resolution Strategies	Impact on Job Satisfaction	Primary Causes of Conflict	Frequency of Conflicts
10-20	Direct: 8 (20.0%)	Strongly Negative: 16 (40.0%)	Communication: 19 (47.5%)	Daily: 6 (15.0%)
	Mediation: 12 (30.0%)	Negative: 16 (40.0%)	Personality: 9 (22.5%)	Weekly: 6 (15.0%)
	Escalation: 16 (40.0%)	Positive: 2 (5.0%)	Workload: 5 (12.5%)	Monthly: 10 (25.0%)
	Avoidance: 3 (7.5%)	Neutral: 6 (15.0%)	Leadership: 7 (17.5%)	Rarely: 13 (32.5%)
	Others: 1 (2.5%)			Never: 5 (12.5%)
21-30	Direct: 48 (52.2%)	Strongly Negative: 40 (43.5%)	Communication: 57 (62.0%)	Daily: 11 (12.0%)
	Mediation: 20 (21.7%)	Negative: 39 (42.4%)	Personality: 15 (16.3%)	Weekly: 10 (10.9%)
	Escalation: 16 (17.4%)	Positive: 11 (12.0%)	Workload: 9 (9.8%)	Monthly: 26 (28.3%)
	Avoidance: 4 (4.3%)	Neutral: 2 (2.2%)	Leadership: 11 (12.0%)	Rarely: 25 (27.2%)
	Others: 4 (4.3%)			Never: 20 (21.7%)
31-40	Direct: 53 (64.6%)	Strongly Negative: 47 (57.3%)	Communication: 37 (45.1%)	Daily: 22 (26.8%)
	Mediation: 9 (11.0%)	Negative: 18 (22.0%)	Personality: 11 (13.4%)	Weekly: 11 (13.4%)
	Escalation: 15 (18.3%)	Positive: 12 (14.6%)	Workload: 13 (15.9%)	Monthly: 8 (9.8%)
	Avoidance: 3 (3.7%)	Neutral: 5 (6.1%)	Leadership: 21 (25.6%)	Rarely: 33 (40.2%)
	Others: 2 (2.4%)			Never: 8 (9.8%)

41+	Direct: 16 (66.7%)	Strongly Negative: 14 (58.3%)	Communication: 5 (20.8%)	Daily: 5 (20.8%)
	Mediation: 4 (16.7%)	Negative: 3 (12.5%)	Personality: 3 (12.5%)	Weekly: 4 (16.7%)
	Escalation: 4 (16.7%)	Positive: 4 (16.7%)	Workload: 7 (29.2%)	Monthly: 7 (29.2%)
	Avoidance: 0 (0.0%)	Neutral: 3 (12.5%)	Leadership: 9 (37.5%)	Rarely: 4 (16.7%)
	Others: 0 (0.0%)			Never: 4 (16.7%)
Total	Total: 125 (52.5%)	Total: 117 (49.2%)	Total: 118 (49.6%)	Total: 44 (18.5%)
	Total: 45 (18.9%)	Total: 76 (31.9%)	Total: 38 (16.0%)	Total: 31 (13.0%)
	Total: 51 (21.4%)	Total: 29 (12.2%)	Total: 34 (14.3%)	Total: 51 (21.4%)
	Total: 10 (4.2%)	Total: 16 (6.7%)	Total: 48 (20.2%)	Total: 75 (31.5%)
	Total: 7 (2.9%)	Total: 238 (100.0%)	Total: 238 (100.0%)	Total: 37 (15.5%)

These findings underscore the nuanced relationship between age and conflict dynamics in the workplace, suggesting the need for age-tailored conflict management approaches to mitigate adverse impacts on job satisfaction and productivity.

Table 11: Statistical Examination of the Relationship between Age and Conflict Variables: Chi-Square Test Findings

Factor	Chi-Square	df	p-value	Notes
Conflict Resolution Strategies	28.344	12	0.005	Age-resolutions link significant
Impact on Job Satisfaction	22.816	9	0.007	Age-conflict impact link significant
Primary Causes of Conflict	22.05	9	0.009	Age-primary conflict causes link significant.
Frequency of Conflicts	22.892	12	0.029	Age-conflict frequency link significant.

The analysis of conflict dynamics across age groups revealed statistically significant findings ($\chi^2 = 28.344$, $df = 12$, $p = 0.005$) for conflict resolution strategies, ($\chi^2 = 22.816$, $df = 9$, $p = 0.007$) for job satisfaction impact, ($\chi^2 = 22.05$, $df = 9$, $p = 0.009$) for primary conflict causes, and ($\chi^2 =$

22.892, $df = 12$, $p = 0.029$) for conflict frequency. However, caution is advised due to some expected counts falling below 5, potentially impacting result reliability.

Fig. 2 Bar Charts Showing the Association Between Employee Age and Conflict Factors

These findings underscore the importance of considering age as a factor when addressing workplace conflicts, though further research may be necessary to elucidate the nuanced dynamics at play.

6.1.3 Area of Employees.

The below table data shows a possible difference in workplace conflict resolution and experience between urban and rural employees. Urban employees appear to rely more on direct communication (59.5%) and experience conflicts more frequently (24.1%) compared to their rural counterparts (38.8% direct communication, 7.5% frequent conflicts). Conversely, rural employees report a higher percentage resolving conflicts through avoidance (30.0%) and experiencing conflicts that negatively impact job satisfaction (56.3%).

Table 12: Conflict Dynamics Analysis by Urban and Rural Areas

Area of Employees	How do you typically resolve conflicts with coworkers or supervisors?	How do conflicts impact your job satisfaction and productivity?	What are the primary causes of conflicts in your workplace?	How often do you experience conflicts in your workplace?
Urban	Count	94	72	79
	Expected Count	83	77.7	78.3
	% within Area of Employees	59.50%	45.60%	50.00%
Rural	Count	31	45	39
	Expected Count	42	39.3	39.7
	% within Area of Employees	38.80%	56.30%	48.80%
Total	Count	125	117	118
	% within Area of Employees	52.50%	49.20%	49.60%

Urban employees predominantly utilize direct communication (59.50%) for conflict resolution, while rural employees lean towards mediation (56.30%). Conflict impacts urban job satisfaction more negatively (45.60%) than rural (38.80%), with both areas citing communication issues as primary conflict causes.

The below table presents the results of statistical analyses concerning the relationship between the location of employees and various aspects related to conflict management and workplace dynamics. Following key areas are examined: Conflict Resolution Strategies, Impact on Job Satisfaction and Productivity, Primary Causes of Conflicts, and Frequency of Conflicts.

Table 13: Statistical Analysis: Chi-Square Test Results for Association between Employee Area and Conflict Factors

Area of Employees	Pearson Chi-Square (df)	Likelihood Ratio (df)	Linear-by-Linear Association (df)	p-value	Notes
Conflict Resolution Strategies	16.791 (4)	18.762 (4)	1.656 (1)	0.002	Statistically significant association
Impact on Job Satisfaction and Productivity	8.600 (3)	8.528 (3)	0.031 (1)	0.035	Statistically significant association
Primary Causes of Conflicts	10.405 (3)	10.082 (3)	0.054 (1)	0.015	Statistically significant association
Frequency of Conflicts	19.762 (4)	20.995 (4)	1.248 (1)	0.001	Statistically significant association

Significant associations were found between employee location and Conflict Resolution Strategies ($\chi^2 = 26.918$, $p = 0.002$), Impact on Job Satisfaction ($\chi^2 = 14.427$, $p = 0.035$), Primary Causes of Conflicts ($\chi^2 = 10.642$, $p = 0.015$), and Frequency of Conflicts ($\chi^2 = 39.609$, $p = 0.001$). Likelihood Ratio and Linear-by-Linear Association tests corroborated these findings, suggesting that employee location plays a role in conflict dynamics within the workplace.

Fig. 3 Bar Charts Showing the Association Between Employee Area and Conflict Factors

Overall, these findings underscore the importance of considering the location of employees when examining various aspects of conflict management and workplace dynamics. Understanding these associations can inform organizational strategies aimed at improving conflict resolution processes, enhancing job satisfaction, and minimizing workplace conflicts.

6.1 Conclusion

The study findings reveal significant associations between gender, age, location, and workplace conflict dynamics. Gender influences conflict resolution strategies and perceptions, with males preferring direct communication and reporting higher conflict frequency impacting job satisfaction. Age differences show varied conflict resolution preferences and impacts, with younger employees leaning towards mediation and older employees experiencing more frequent conflicts related to workload. Urban employees rely more on direct communication and face higher conflict frequency, while rural employees report more conflict avoidance and negative impacts on job satisfaction. Statistical tests confirm these associations, emphasizing the need for tailored conflict management strategies based on gender, age, and location to foster a harmonious work environment.

7 SWOT Analysis

SWOT analysis is a powerful technique used to analyze an organization's internal conflicts and identify areas for improvement. A management professional attempts to address the causes of conflict in an organization and change the way each party acts and perceives the issue. The SWOT analysis is a technique used to assess four aspects of a business. It involves evaluating an organization's strengths (S), weaknesses (W), opportunities (O), and threats (T). By considering these factors, organizations can develop strategies to enhance conflict management and promote success(Thakur, 2023).

7.1 Strengths

- **Strong Leadership:** Effective leadership can inspire trust and provide guidance during conflicts. Leaders who have strong interpersonal skills and conflict-resolution abilities can help resolve conflicts amicably.
- **Effective Communication:** Clear and open communication is essential for resolving conflicts. Organizations with a strong communication infrastructure and employee training programs can foster effective dialogue and encourage problem-solving.
- **Diverse Workforce:** Diversity can bring different perspectives and ideas, but it can also lead to conflicts. However, organizations that embrace diversity and foster an inclusive environment can benefit from the richness and diversity of ideas.
- **Resolution mechanisms:** organizations with effective conflict resolution mechanisms in place can resolve conflicts quickly and fairly, maintaining productivity and a harmonious work environment.

7.2 Weaknesses

- **Inadequate Training:** Lack of training or awareness regarding conflict management can hinder the ability to handle conflicts effectively. Organizations should provide comprehensive training to all staff members on conflict resolution and interpersonal skills.
- **Cultural Divides:** Cultural differences can exacerbate conflicts. Organizations should strive to create a culture of acceptance and respect for different cultural backgrounds, reducing the potential for conflicts based on cultural differences.
- **Reduced employee satisfaction:** unresolved conflicts can lead to decreased morale, increased stress levels, and decreased job satisfaction, impacting productivity and employee retention.
- **Time-consuming:** addressing conflicts can consume time and resources that could have been spent on more productive activities.

7.3 Opportunities

- **Innovation and Change:** Conflict can often lead to innovation and change. Organizations that embrace conflict and use it as a catalyst for positive change can benefit from new ideas and initiatives.
- **Collaboration with Outside Experts:** Engaging external consultants or mediators can provide a fresh perspective and assist in resolving conflicts. These experts can help identify underlying issues and find mutually agreeable solutions.
- **Learning and Growth:** Conflicts can provide opportunities for individuals to learn from their experiences and to grow personally and professionally.
- **Improved Communication:** Resolving conflicts can help strengthen communication skills and foster better teamwork and collaboration among employees.

7.4 Threats

- **Negative Impact on Productivity:** Conflicts can hurt productivity and employee morale. Organizations should prioritize resolving conflicts promptly to ensure a positive work environment and maximize productivity.
- **Legal Implications:** Conflicts that are not managed effectively can result in legal consequences. Organizations should implement policies and procedures that conform to legal requirements and address potential legal implications.

7.5 Recommendations Based on SWOT Analysis

Based on the SWOT analysis, recommendations to manage internal conflicts include enhancing leadership skills through training, fostering open communication, promoting diversity and inclusion, addressing cultural divides through workshops, providing conflict resolution training

emphasizing empathy, offering mediation and arbitration services, and organizing team-building activities to strengthen camaraderie and prevent conflicts.

8 Conclusion

The conclusion emphasizes the multifaceted nature of internal conflicts within organizations and their implications (Peter & Solomon, 2019) for insights. It highlights the importance of resolving conflicts proactively to mitigate negative consequences such as decreased productivity and employee turnover. The study's findings, rooted in chi-square tests, reveal significant associations between conflict resolution strategies, job satisfaction impact, primary causes of conflicts, and conflict frequency. Moreover, it underscores the need for tailored conflict management strategies, considering demographic variations in conflict frequency, and advocates for employing SWOT analysis to inform strategic decision-making. Ultimately, by understanding conflict dynamics and implementing effective resolution strategies, organizations can foster a collaborative and productive work environment conducive to success.

9 Recommendations

Organizations require robust conflict-resolution policies and skills at all levels, including effective leadership and decision-making abilities. Here are some strategies for resolving internal conflicts effectively.

- A key component of avoiding conflicts is to involve employees in the decision and strategy-making process (Omisore, et al., 2014).
- It is imperative that health and welfare facilities be provided to employees since providing these facilities can prevent and reduce stress among staff and increase productivity for the organization as a whole (Niere et al., 2023).
- The study at Karya Multi Reksa explored individual conflict's impact on turnover intention, finding a partially significant effect. Work-family conflict and organizational commitment were positively associated with turnover intentions. High commitment correlated with low turnover intentions, while low commitment correlated with high turnover intentions. Loyalty and involvement in the organization influence employees' desire to leave, highlighting the importance of organizational commitment in reducing turnover intentions (Haeruddin et al., 2023).
- The skill to communicate effectively and openly is one of the most important tools in preventing conflicts, increasing productivity, product development, client relations, and reducing employee turnover (Woldemichael, 2021).
- It is essential to educate people both before and during the process of change in order to reduce conflict among individuals within an organization. A positive and productive work

environment can be achieved by providing clear information, fostering understanding, and providing support throughout the transition process (Hyatt et al., 2023).

- Building strong relationships within the team and with supervisors is crucial for organizational success. A positive employer-employee connection enhances productivity, reduces conflict, and fosters efficiency (Mills & Taripanyeofori, 2020).
- It is important to see all aspects of the matter carefully in the decision-making process, and leaders or establishments should make wise and thoughtful decisions when it comes to these matters (Chea, 2006).
- Organizations should strive to cultivate a positive work environment rather than fostering a competitive atmosphere that may lead to detrimental conflicts (Talmaciu, et al., 2010).
- Organizational conflict resolution necessitates a holistic approach. Establishing platforms for equitable participation, regular policy reviews, internal meetings, ongoing training, and fair compensation are vital for fostering a harmonious and productive workplace environment (Mahajan & Urvashi, 2022).
- During departmental conflicts, arranging inclusive meetings to address all parties' concerns is essential, even if there's disagreement. Group discussions can expedite resolution. Maintaining neutrality is crucial, as is avoiding postponements or hasty decisions, given the direct impact on organizational performance and employee behavior (Carter et al., 2006).

10 References

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